

Emerging Trends of the Social Contract: Navigating the Complex Interplay between Development and Authoritarianism

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Abstract: As authoritarianism becomes more prominent globally, the traditional concept of the “social contract” ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#)) is undergoing a significant transformation that often goes unnoticed. This essay strives to reevaluate the conceptual foundations of the social contract by examining development and authoritarianism from the South Asian perspective. Although Bangladesh has been chosen as a central case study, the underlying issues within the scope of the study have incorporated the global scenario as well. Bangladesh exemplifies how “clientelist politics” ([Kitschelt & Wilkinson, 2007](#); [Chandra, 2004](#)), the suppression of dissent, the erosion of democratic institutions, and widespread human rights abuses lead to a growing legitimacy crisis. Despite having electoral processes in place, the country displays many traits of competitive authoritarianism ([Levitsky & Way, 2010](#)). The state laws are manipulated to consolidate control and disempower opposition. The outcomes of such a political climate include a decline in public trust, restricted civic engagement, and increased inequality, all indicative of a broken social contract. By incorporating Rousseau’s philosophical ideas, historical colonial influences, and contemporary governance, this essay investigates the emergence of illiberal democracies, the exploitation of populism, and the false sense of progress in authoritarian regimes that favor development over freedom. Given this context, the paper suggests finding a way to reconcile Rousseau’s idealism with Hume’s skepticism, responding to criticisms that Hume weakens the basis for contractual legitimacy. Through an in-depth examination of institutional legitimacy and the viability of autocratic development, the paper calls for a revitalized moral vision of the social contract—focused on dignity, justice, and inclusive governance. Ultimately, it urges both Eastern and Western societies to harmonize political authority with human values in an increasingly uncertain world ([Snyder, 2017](#)).

Keywords: Social Contract, Development, Authoritarianism, Inclusive Governance, Human Rights, Political Economy of Bangladesh

1. Introduction

The concept of the “nation-state” is commonly translated as having defined borders, a shared identity, and a collective sense of belonging. Yet, in South Asia, this textbook version confronts a far more complicated reality. Unlike Europe, where political boundaries typically emerged from socio-cultural context, or the United States, where a diverse “state-nation” became possible through a deliberately crafted social contract based on liberty, justice, and moral vision ([Habermas, 1996](#); [Rawls, 1971](#)). South Asian borders were drawn in colonial boardrooms, focusing on rulers rather than the people ([Anderson, 2006](#); [Chatterjee, 1993](#)). The consequence of this is the creation of fragmented political entities with weak civic bonds and contested ideas of “nationhood.”

These historical patterns in the nation-building context seemingly reflect perpetual administrative frameworks rather than a deeply felt, unified identity. The mutual trust between government and the citizens significantly deteriorates when a strong, values-based social contract remains absent. This foundational agreement, which relies on mutually inclusive consent, warrants the governance to hold moral accountability, and the dearth of it compels the state to face significant challenges ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#); [Hume, 1748/1985](#)).

In countries like Bangladesh, this context largely fuels patronage based politics ([Kitschelt & Wilkinson, 2007](#); [Chandra, 2004](#)), flawed electoral systems, the repression of opposing opinion, and an increase in authoritarianism—all signs of a social contract under significant strain ([Human Rights Watch, 2023](#)).

This essay examines how the distorted views on governance, developmental drives devoid of justice and equity, and gradual compelled acceptance of authoritarianism are transforming the political landscape in South Asia. By

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revisiting classical social contract theories—from Rousseau's emphasis on the "general will" to Hume's skepticism about hypothetical consent—it argues that these issues are not just constitutional or economic but also deeply moral in nature. Furthermore, it suggests that in order to ensure a viable, dignified, purposeful, and sustainable future, the global community must harmonize authority with accountability, power with principles, and modern development with the cultural and ethical foundations of the societies it seeks to serve.

2. Problem Statement

Despite rapid economic and social development across many post-colonial nations in South Asia, a growing legitimacy crisis is evident due to authoritarian tendencies, patronage politics, and weakened social contracts. Existing governance structures often prioritize short-term economic outcomes over human dignity, civic participation, and justice, undermining long-term stability and inclusive growth. This study asks: How does authoritarian development interact with the erosion of the social contract in South Asian contexts, and what lessons can be drawn to reconcile development with inclusive governance, particularly in countries like Bangladesh?

3. Literature Review

3.1 Social Contract Theory in Comparative Perspective

The concept of the social contract has long served as a framework to understand legitimacy, governance, and citizen–state relations. Classical theorists such as Rousseau (1762/2010) emphasized that legitimate political authority arises from the “general will,” underpinned by unanimous consent and moral accountability. In contrast, Hume (1748/1985) critiqued the notion of hypothetical consent, arguing that political authority evolves through custom, habit, and gradual acceptance rather than rational agreements. Modern scholars such as Rawls (1971) and Sen (1999, 2009) have extended this debate, highlighting the importance of justice, equity, and human capabilities as essential components of a viable social contract. This theoretical discourse provides a lens through which governance structures in South Asia can be evaluated, particularly when authoritarian practices threaten civic trust and inclusivity.

3.2. Authoritarianism and Development in South Asia

Recent studies illustrate a nuanced relationship between authoritarianism and development in post-colonial contexts. Leftwich (1995) and Kohli (2004) argue that strong, centralized states can achieve rapid economic growth by bypassing bureaucratic and political obstacles, a phenomenon often labeled “authoritarian developmentalism.” Hale (2014) identifies the prevalence of patronal politics, corruption, and personalistic leadership as defining characteristics of these regimes, which rely on co-optation and clientelism to maintain power. Levitsky & Way (2010) further describe competitive authoritarianism, where democratic institutions exist in form but are undermined in practice, highlighting the fragility of legitimacy in such systems.

Empirical studies from South Asia, particularly Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan, illustrate the costs of these governance models. Kitschelt & Wilkinson (2007) and Chandra (2004) document how patronage networks and clientelist politics distort electoral processes, reduce transparency, and restrict civic engagement. Fukuyama (2013) and Acemoglu & Robinson (2012) emphasize that while authoritarian regimes can deliver impressive GDP growth, these gains often come at the expense of social equity, political freedoms, and long-term institutional stability.

3.3. Erosion of Social Contracts and Inequality

A weakened social contract manifests in declining public trust, restricted political participation, and the concentration of wealth among elites. Fraser (1997) and Stiglitz (2012) argue that neoliberal policies, deregulation, and austerity measures exacerbate inequality, while Polanyi's (1944) “double movement” concept suggests that societal pushback occurs when market forces undermine social protections. In South Asia, these dynamics are evident in widening urban-rural disparities, exclusion of marginalized communities, and the suppression of dissent, highlighting the gap between formal governance structures and lived realities.

3.4. Integrating Development, Justice, and Civic Engagement

Scholars increasingly advocate for reconciling developmental objectives with inclusive governance. Sen (1999) emphasizes that freedom and capability expansion are central to human development, while Sobhan (2010) argues that development must address structural inequalities and ensure participation from all social strata. Snyder (2017) warns that authoritarian populism can exploit economic or social insecurities to legitimize control, thereby eroding democratic norms and the moral foundations of governance.

Recent case studies from Bangladesh demonstrate these tensions. Despite consistent GDP growth, patronage politics, selective law enforcement, and curbs on civil liberties have led to diminished legitimacy and widespread public dissatisfaction (Human Rights Watch, 2023). This mirrors trends across South Asia, where rapid development under authoritarian-leaning governments often fails to produce durable social contracts or inclusive progress.

3.5 Research Gap

While existing literature robustly addresses the intersections of authoritarianism and development, there remains a significant gap in exploring how these processes interact with the erosion of social contracts in South Asia, especially with respect to moral legitimacy, civic participation, and inclusive governance. Few studies offer an integrative framework combining classical social contract theory (Rousseau, Hume), modern normative perspectives (Rawls, Sen), and empirical evidence from South Asian case studies. This study seeks to fill that gap by examining the interplay between authoritarian development and the social contract, using Bangladesh as a central but not exclusive example.

4. Research Questions

- a. How do authoritarian development policies impact the social contract and legitimacy in South Asian nations?
- b. What is the relationship between development outcomes and civic trust under authoritarian regimes?
- c. How does erosion of social contract principles affect human development, social equity, and citizen engagement?
- d. What governance mechanisms can reconcile rapid development with legitimacy, human dignity, and inclusive participation?

5. Research Objectives

- a. To analyze the effects of authoritarian development policies on social contract erosion and legitimacy in South Asia.
- b. To examine the relationship between development outcomes and civic trust under centralized governance.
- c. To assess the consequences of weakened social contracts on human development and social equity.
- d. To identify policy and governance mechanisms that can harmonize development with inclusive and legitimate governance.

6. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study illustrates the interplay between authoritarian development, the social contract, and legitimacy, and how these relationships affect civic trust, social equity, and human development outcomes in South Asia. The framework connects theoretical ideas (Rousseau's social contract, Sen's human development) with observed governance dynamics.

Key concepts and relationships:

- a. Authoritarian Development
 - i. Centralized decision-making and rapid economic growth.
 - ii. Limited political pluralism and restricted civic participation.
 - iii. May achieve short-term developmental gains but risk long-term institutional fragility.
- b. Social Contract
 - i. Reciprocal obligations between citizens and the state.
 - ii. Under authoritarianism, citizens' consent is weakened, undermining legitimacy.
- c. Legitimacy & Trust
 - i. Derived from adherence to the social contract and perception of fairness.
 - ii. Affected by law enforcement, transparency, and institutional stability.
- d. Human Dignity & Equity

- i. Distribution of wealth, access to justice, and freedom of participation.
- ii. Weak social contracts often produce inequities, social exclusion, and dissatisfaction.

Fig-1: illustrates the interplay between authoritarian development, the social contract, and legitimacy, and how these relationships affect civic trust, social equity, and human development outcomes in South Asia.

7. Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in multiple theoretical perspectives to provide a comprehensive lens for analyzing governance, development, and legitimacy in South Asia.

Social Contract Theory forms the philosophical foundation, drawing on Rousseau's notion of the "general will," which emphasizes citizens' consent and the reciprocal obligations of the state. Complementing this, Hume's historical skepticism about consent highlights the complexities and often imperfect realization of social contracts in real-world governance. Together, these perspectives allow the study to interrogate how state authority aligns—or misaligns—with the expectations and rights of citizens.

Developmental State Theory (Kohli, 2004; Leftwich, 1995) provides a framework to understand how states can drive rapid economic growth through centralized planning and policy interventions. This theory helps explain the appeal and mechanisms of authoritarian development models, where efficiency and output are often prioritized over participatory governance.

Authoritarianism and Political Economy perspectives (Hale, 2014; Levitsky & Way, 2010; O'Donnell, 1973) contribute insights on the durability, strategies, and consequences of concentrated political power. They illuminate how patronage networks, institutional weaknesses, and constrained civic engagement interact with development objectives, shaping both legitimacy and trust.

Finally, Sen's Human Capabilities Approach (1992, 1999, 2009) anchors the study in normative development concerns, emphasizing human dignity, freedom, and equity as essential outcomes. By integrating this framework, the research evaluates whether growth under authoritarian regimes translates into genuine improvements in human development or whether it comes at the cost of social legitimacy and civic participation.

Integration of Theories: By bridging classical philosophy, modern development theory, and political economy, the study assesses the tensions and synergies between authoritarian governance, social contract legitimacy, and development outcomes. This integrated framework allows for a nuanced exploration of whether South Asian states can reconcile rapid growth with inclusive, participatory, and equitable governance.

8. Research Framework

8.1 Methodology

This research uses an objective analytical approach, referencing a mix of literature from political theory, development studies, and governance. It synthesizes classical and modern social contract theories, integrating recent analyses of authoritarianism to investigate the decline of social contract principles in Bangladesh. The study uses theory and data extracted from policy reports and human rights documents to evaluate Bangladesh's situation within the global and regional context. This enables an in-depth exploration of the linkages between authoritarian governance, social justice, and sustainable development, contributing to discussions on fair, just, and inclusive governance models.

8.2 Analytical Framework

8.2.1 Purpose: Systematically examine how authoritarian development interacts with social contract erosion and affects legitimacy, civic trust, and human development outcomes.

8.2.2 Approach: Qualitative, comparative case study of South Asian nations, focusing on Bangladesh as a central example.

8.2.3 Data Sources

- i. Policy documents and government reports
- ii. Human Rights Watch and Transparency International reports
- iii. Secondary datasets on development, inequality, and governance

8.2.4 Analysis Steps

- i. Trend Analysis: Track authoritarian policies and development outcomes over time.
- ii. Social Contract Assessment: Evaluate erosion of citizen-state obligations using Rousseau-Hume theoretical lens.
- iii. Gap Analysis: Compare formal institutions' promises with citizens' lived experiences.

- iv. Policy Evaluation: Identify governance mechanisms that can reconcile rapid development with legitimacy and civic trust.

8.2.5 Simple Functional Relationship

Let:

- L= Legitimacy & Civic Trust
- A = Authoritarian Policies
- D= Development Outcomes
- S = Social Contract Erosion

$$L = D - (A + S)$$

Interpretation:

- Legitimacy rises with better development outcomes (DDD)
- Legitimacy falls as authoritarian practices (AAA) or social contract erosion (SSS) increase
- This single function captures the core dynamics for systematic analysis

3. Background Overview: Western Social Contract and Its Authoritarian Challenge

The very essence of the social contract is evident in Western democracies. These societies have experienced decades of political struggles and philosophical developments, leading to a social system characterized by mutually inclusive consent. This consent is the central thematic component and driving force of governance, which has evolved over the course of time, although it may not be free of imperfection. In this context, the social contract is not just an abstract concept; it serves as a vital foundation for law, justice, and public confidence ([Snyder, 2017](#)).

However, applying these societal models to vastly different cultural contexts has often proven unsuccessful. Many post-colonial countries, including Bangladesh, face challenges rooted in histories of oppression, arbitrary borders, and fragmented identities. These "state-nations," which arose from colonialism rather than a shared aspiration, lacked the opportunity to develop a cohesive national identity based on the state. What they need, and continue to need, is a robust foundational social contract that can unite diverse groups into a cohesive, inclusive, and people-focused state.

Interestingly, while some liberal democracies struggle with issues like inequality and political disillusionment, certain authoritarian governments have achieved significant development results. Through centralized authority and swift policy implementation, these regimes have managed to lift millions out of poverty, often neglecting the essential social structures necessary for lasting civic well-being. However, beneath these economic improvements lies a troubling emptiness defined by a lack of genuine participation, distrust in institutions, and dissent.

For objectively outlining the key differences between the liberal-democratic view of the social contract and the authoritarian approach, a scrutiny of the purpose and nature of development models pursued by authoritarian states is necessary, as these often disregard the individual rights. It is also necessary to look into the reasons and mechanism behind the seeming popularity of some of the authoritarian models, particularly in situations where democratic institutions are weak ([Hale, 2014](#)). In this context, this paper argues that while development achieved without a robust social contract may lead to immediate success, it ultimately rests on a shaky foundation for the future, lacking civic trust, moral legitimacy and sustainability.

Bangladesh is currently at a crucial point in its development. The objective is not just to attain growth but to ensure that this growth honors and upholds the dignity of citizens. This means creating a social contract that is original and tailored to the country-specific needs, responsive to its citizens, and strong enough to handle the challenges of the 21st century.

4. Rousseau's Philosophy: Free Will, Consent, and the General Will

Humans are free beings, unlike other creatures; we are not entirely driven by instinct or biological forces. We actively choose our goals and how to pursue them. Despite our capacity for deep freedom, societies impose constraints on how we exercise it.

Rousseau argues that our uniqueness lies in free will, not rationality or compassion, which some animals also possess. He rejects the idea of a "right of the strongest," asserting that true rights claim respect even in the absence of force. If someone subjugates us through power rather than consent, we only need to obey them as long as they are stronger. Rousseau also argues that individuals cannot legitimately forfeit their rights or be subjected to the arbitrary will of another.

Rousseau further posits that a society can have legitimate and absolute authority over citizens if it meets two conditions: it must be founded on unanimous consent, and the agreement must recognize the "general will" as sovereign over the society and its laws. The "general will" ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#)) is the unified will of the people. When the social contract is ratified, individual wills combine to form a new collective entity: a republic. He also thinks that neither a democratic majority nor a single ruler can justly impose laws we disapprove of. The general will allows society to enforce laws without infringing on individual liberty.

5. Criticism of the Social Contract & the Origins of Government

The social contract theory has been the subject of critique from various philosophers. David Hume stands out as a prominent figure in this discourse, raising valuable questions regarding the foundations of the theory. Hume regarded the social contract as a 'historical fiction,' meaning it was a mental fabrication, an intellectual construct that inaccurately depicted the origins of political communities ([Hume, 1748/1985](#)).

In his article 'Of the Original Contract,' Hume (1748) contends that political institutions are seldom founded on rational agreements or free assent. Rather, political systems develop through historical progression that often includes invasion and takeover, leading to a gradual increase in power. Hume suggests that political authority isn't created through formal agreements but instead arises from the customs and habits of the people and their continuous acceptance of it ([Hume, 1748/1985](#)).

Hume also contests the presumption that underpins the notion of human beings as predominantly rational agents who make political decisions based on self-interest. Hume asserts that human action is predominantly influenced by passions, emotions, and social habits rather than rationality ([Hume, 1739/2007](#)).

Hume believed that true sovereignty comes not just from reason and its rationale but also from custom. As societies evolve, they create various political institutions, and when people accept these changes and appreciate the benefits of stability and order, they are perceived as legitimate. For Hume, legitimacy doesn't stem from agreements based on rational discussions; it essentially implies that, it's natural for people to view existing social structures as unavoidable ([Hume, 1748/1985](#)).

6. Bringing Together Hume and Rousseau in Practice

6.1 An Easy Way to Reconciliation

A just society doesn't need to decide between Hume's emotions and Rousseau's rational and logical conclusions. Rather, justice can be conceptualized as a simultaneous process, combining the natural human sentiments of fairness, empathy, and reciprocity with structured interactive discussions and agreements. This approach allows us to keep the emotional connections that unite communities while also putting them into formal systems like laws, constitutions, rights, and rigid frameworks. Justice isn't just a matter of emotions or pure logic; it's about working together by combining our feelings with our reasoning. Thus, we create justice collaboratively rather than imposing it from above or letting it arise from below.

6.2 Theoretical Underpinnings

This hybrid approach combines Hume's idea that moral standards come from usefulness and emotions with contract theory, which views justice as the result of fair agreements between rational individuals. Thinkers like Rawls, who are advocates of contract theory, also stresses on common moral feelings to support concepts such as fairness and equality ([Rawls, 1971](#)). Rawls argues for a principled balance between liberty and equality that should be applied to the basic framework of a well-ordered society. Acting as a unifying framework, Amartya Sen's capabilities approach seemingly bridges this divide by focusing on what people have reason to value—both in being and in doing ([Sen, 2009](#)). Reconciliation, therefore, does not mean choosing one tradition over the other, but rather creating a new understanding where reason builds structures upon the foundations of shared moral feeling. Justice is thus seen as a fluid process of developing norms, not just a fixed agreement or a random emotion.

6.3 The Bangladeshi Context

In Bangladesh, this reconciliation is not merely a matter of philosophy; it is politically significant and pressing.

The inheritance of colonial legal frameworks and the constitutionalism that followed independence exemplify a contract-based approach, whereas grassroots moral feelings, religious principles, and community ties embody a more Humean basis for moral order. A just society here requires more than imported frameworks; it must respect local sentiment while promoting rational inclusivity. Bridging Hume and the contractarians allows Bangladesh to move beyond imposed ideologies and build a just society rooted in both moral legitimacy and institutional stability.

7. Some Contested Concepts within the Scope of the Paper

7.1 Authoritarianism and Social Contract

The relationship between authoritarianism and the social contract is complex and debated. O'Donnell (1973) puts forward the argument that authoritarian regimes often give priority to security and economic stability over political freedoms, implying a trade-off between individual liberties and state control. (O'Donnell, 1973).

However, this arrangement is inevitably unstable and severely undermines sustainability. As observed, such "contracts" do not have the lasting texture of democratic legitimacy. Even though these regimes are neither actively devoted to Rousseau's notion of popular consent nor subject to anything like its ideal form, they fabricate a sense of legitimacy through their well-planned governance structure and intricately disguised control mechanisms. Nevertheless, failure to fulfill contractual and constitutional obligations may lead to the failure of the social contract and simmering discontent among the people (Rousseau, 1762/2010).

7.2 Authoritarianism and Development in Theoretical Perspective

The question of authoritarianism and development has been debated for many years. Those in favor of authoritarian regimes assert that authoritarian regimes ensure accelerated economic growth by avoiding political barriers and consolidating state power. (Leftwich, 1995; Kohli, 2004). Those who oppose this stance, argue that such growth is usually exclusionary, ecologically dangerous, and founded on repression.

- Arguments for Authoritarianism:

Its advocates assert that authoritarian regimes can avoid the bureaucratic obstacles and consensus-building process that mark democratic governments, thus facilitating the swift execution of large-scale infrastructure and economic projects. With minimal political opposition, these governments seemingly can ensure policy stability and engage in long-term planning (Haggard, 1990). Some also believe that centralized governments are more prompt in mobilizing resources and effectively implementing national development agendas. In this context, it can be added that democracy is considered as more suitable for economically advanced countries; conversely, dictatorship is seemingly more effective in the less advanced societies where social contract is not robust. (Przeworski et al., 2000; Rodrik, 2000).

- Arguments against Authoritarianism:

Critics of authoritarianism contend that it hinders inclusive and sustainable development by restricting civil rights. Additionally, it weakens participatory governance systems (Sen, 1999). Authoritarian governments accumulate wealth and power, resulting in marginalized communities being deprived of critical services (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). Non-democratic governments often have the traits of favoritism and corruption; this phenomenon leads to unequal and inequitable wealth distribution. Furthermore, the lack of public accountability lowers the state's long-term planning horizons and effectiveness in responding to crises (Transparency International, 2023). Authoritarian leaders often prioritize short-term political survival over sustainable development in environments lacking citizen participation and transparency.

In conclusion, while authoritarianism may provide a pathway to accelerated infrastructure development or increased GDP growth, it often does so at the expense of human rights, inclusivity, equity, and future stability. Democratic governance, despite being slow to progress, is a better and fairer basis for achieving sustainable development which also promotes human dignity and freedom of choice (Fukuyama, 2013; Sen, 1999).

7.3 Eroding Social Contract and Inequitable Wealth Distribution

The weakening of the social contract is a big reason for the uptrend of economic inequality around the world. Traditionally, the social contract means that people give consent to support the state by being loyal, following laws, and paying taxes, while the state promises to provide safety, services, and equal chances for all (Rousseau, 1762/2010; Locke, 1988). However, today this agreement is collapsing. Policies like neoliberalism, austerity,

deregulation, and reduced government assistance have created drastic inequalities. Thus, the wealth is accumulated in the hands of a few people, and others believe that they are left behind (Fraser, 1997). This has resulted in increased political dissatisfaction and social unrest (Stiglitz, 2012). [Polanyi \(1944\)](#) argued that unregulated markets and the erosion of social protections destabilize societies. In response, communities engage in a “double movement,” mobilizing to restore protections and rebalance the relationship between market forces and social needs. This process parallels the renegotiation of the social contract itself.

7.4 Social Contract and Social Justice

Social contract theory establishes the foundation for fairness and justice in a society. Thinkers such as John Rawls and Amartya Sen are strong advocates of this idea. They also prioritize that fairness in sharing rights, responsibilities, and opportunities is an essential component of any society ([Rawls, 1971](#); [Sen, 2009](#)). Social justice, in the social contract sense, requires that every citizen should be given equal protection under the law and equal access to public resources engaged in the welfare and development of individuals. In *Inequality Reexamined* (1992), Sen argues that we should pay attention not only to how primary goods are distributed but also to how effectively individuals can utilize those goods to achieve their goals. ([Sen, 1992](#))

Civil rights legislation safeguards against discrimination and guarantees voting rights. These rights serve as a legal framework that embodies and reinforces the contractarian ideals. When these protections fail or are selectively enforced, the social contract breaks down, and consequently, it requires reform and restitution ([Habermas, 1996](#)).

8. Evolving Trends of Authoritarianism and Development

8.1 Authoritarianism on the Rise: Hale’s Patronal Politics and the New Global Trend

In recent years, there has been a notable resurgence of authoritarianism. In *Patronal Politics*, Henry Hale compellingly examines the traits that define authoritarian regimes, including their autocratic tendencies, corruption, personalistic leadership, and reliance on patronage. He delves into the intricate dynamics of these systems, providing insights into why some authoritarian governments trigger mass protests while others remain unchallenged, relating this to the leadership skills of those in power ([Hale, 2014](#)). Although more countries are conducting elections, these often lack genuine competitiveness, leading to terms like “illiberal democracies” and “semi-authoritarianism” ([Levitsky & Way, 2010](#)). Historically, the Romans viewed democracy as similar to mob rule and preferred liberty and the rule of law instead. However, the rule of law is crucial to the social contract framework and should be embraced as a fundamental principle. By integrating religious and social values, we can significantly strengthen the rule of law, ensuring that justice and fairness remain central to our moral and legal systems ([Snyder, 2017](#)).

8.2 The Populist Dilemma and the Threat to Democratic Norms

Authoritarian developmentalism can adopt a populist character within this context. In contemporary politics, we observe that some populist leaders can obtain democratic mandates while advocating for policies that may challenge traditional liberal democratic values. This phenomenon may strengthen authoritarian regimes, which take advantage of the uncertainties arising from populist movements to critique democratic governance ([Snyder, 2017](#)). Authoritarian populist leaders frequently scapegoat minority groups for societal problems, especially in ethnically diverse countries. This can lead to persecution and a collapse of the social contract. In more homogeneous states, the emphasis usually shifts to external threats, prioritizing security over health and social care. This situation leads to a cycle where governance declines and nationalism rises. Such a trend poses a considerable risk, as countries may start to lean more towards authoritarianism.

8.3 Development without Liberty: The Mirage of Authoritarian Growth

Development without liberty leads to increased poverty, sustainability in growth, repression of political and civil rights, and more specifically, these approaches can contribute to the widening of inequality, as seen in the historical trajectories of stricter authoritarian states. This growing inequality can exacerbate the complexities of the social contract. Some authoritarian growth overlooks the pivotal role of human dignity, freedom to make choices and pursuance of one’s personal goals in achieving lasting growth and prosperity. The very purpose of human development in the civilizational context cannot be fulfilled without being culture sensitive. Over the past decade, Bangladesh has seen impressive GDP growth; however, this progress has largely overlooked the distribution of wealth. This disparity reveals a critical weakness in the social contract, highlighting the need for

a more inclusive and equitable approach to development ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#)).

8.4 Complex Interplay: Authoritarianism, Balanced Social Contract and the Sustainability of Development

In many instances, the development strategies put forth by authoritarian regimes may face challenges in ensuring long-term sustainability. In certain cases, authoritarian states have demonstrated remarkable development, yet this progress comes at a significant cost: the erosion of a balanced social contract. These states undermine individual freedoms and degrade the fundamental values that uphold social cohesion. This scenario results in deepening inequalities and the looming threat of widespread social unrest. The stability of these states is seemingly at risk, often jeopardizing their very existence. Such conditions not only fail to honor human dignity but actually degrade it.

Despite these challenges, it is important to recognize that some mechanisms exist that manage to lift a substantial segment of the population out of poverty, even in the absence of a robust social contract. This may be due to inherent social mechanisms, age-old socio-political doctrine, or longstanding social bonds that prevent rapid fragmentation of social and political structures, allowing for sustained authoritarian development. The critical question remains: can these mechanisms be sustained over time within the existing framework of the nation-state? Establishing this sustainability is vital for ensuring long-term development that respects and upholds human dignity for all.

8.5 Urban-Rural Gaps and Cultural Conflicts

When we consider the social contract as a commitment to meet people's material needs, it becomes clear that a stark disparity exists in the distribution of economic wealth between rural and urban areas. This gap is especially pronounced in certain economically advanced countries with authoritarian regimes, which rank among the highest in global inequality ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#)). Addressing this gap is crucial for social cohesion and equitable development. The policymakers should consider the unique needs of urban and rural areas while allocating resources and strategizing development so that it ensures equitable resource distribution. Additionally, the swift pace of urbanization can lead to considerable cultural and normative conflicts. Addressing these differences is crucial for fostering social cohesion and ensuring equitable resource distribution.

9. Case Study: Bangladesh and the Erosion of Social Contract Principles—Way Forward

Bangladesh presents a striking example of a fractured social contract, where a corrupted electoral process has led to widespread disenfranchisement among the population. Too often, people confuse the concept of a social contract with mere development, allowing those in power to exploit the struggles of the populace. Without a reliable framework for subsistence, many individuals are compelled to overlook the fundamental principles of social contract theory. Sometimes, even the most vulnerable groups support tyrants due to immediate survival needs. They prioritize their struggle for subsistence over their rightful involvement in the production and distribution of resources, as well as their general will. This reality enables corrupt leaders and their supporters to engage in capital flight without facing any consequences. Most troubling is the fact that some authoritarian regimes have managed to create a facade of progress while neglecting a true social contract, thereby challenging the core principles of human dignity and rights. Such situations not only threaten the well-being of the citizens but also undermine the foundations of a just society.

Bangladesh has been experiencing a worrying trend of democratic crises, characterized by the erosion of the social contract and the rise of authoritarian tendencies.

9.1 Erosion of the Social Contract

Bangladesh experienced a decline in public trust in the recent past, which is indicative of the damaged social contract within the broader community. This deteriorating situation is largely propelled by government actions, which include alleged election manipulation, human rights abuses, and the implementation of oppressive laws. These actions have weakened confidence in state institutions. The former government was accused of practicing patronage politics ([Kitschelt & Wilkinson, 2007](#); [Chandra, 2004](#)), where the people were granted access to opportunity and resources on the basis of political loyalty rather than fairness or merit. Additionally, the above exclusion and discrimination were specifically aimed at politically marginalized populations, who were devoid of access to education, work, and civil rights. This phenomenon further strains the social fabric of the country. Furthermore, public participation in local governance and development processes is structurally constrained, leading to widespread feelings of disengagement and alienation among the populace.

9.2 Rise of Authoritarian Tendencies

The rise of authoritarianism in Bangladesh is reflected in a number of worrying trends. The government has been accused of suppressing dissent by using laws such as the Digital Security Act (DSA), targeting political rivals, critics, and journalists, and thereby restricting the freedom of expression and assembly. Human rights abuses—among them extrajudicial killings, torture, and enforced disappearances—particularly against dissidents, have raised grave doubts about the state's commitment to basic rights. Democratic institutions have been weakened due to alleged interference with the judiciary, which undermines the separation of powers.

Additionally, the state has been accused of exploiting existing laws. Government also introduced new legislation, such as the Digital Services Act (DSA), in order to silence criticism, repress press freedom and consolidate its power ([Human Rights Watch, 2023](#)).

9.3 Governance, Misinformation, and Institutional Legitimacy

For the social contract between citizens and government to thrive, it is crucial for the public to trust the accuracy of government statements and believe that institutions prioritize the common good. The government must actively dispel misinformation and create policies that serve national interests rather than specific groups. In Bangladesh, government has been associated with the dissemination of misleading information, which has had implications for the public discourse. In our digital age, ensuring access to reliable information while maintaining trust in government is more essential than ever ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#)).

9.4 Protests, Fractures, and the Call for Inclusive Protection Systems

The recent uprising in Bangladesh has starkly highlighted the profound divisions in the society, igniting widespread protests and escalating social tensions. If this harmful cycle continues unchecked, the risk of further fragmentation increases. Yet, there is a way forward across countries: embracing inclusive social protection systems while striving to build a diverse and developed society. By putting these systems in place, the developing nations can restore trust in the institutions, which is vital for fostering social cohesion. This change is not just a reaction to existing challenges; it's a crucial step toward establishing a virtuous cycle sustained by inclusiveness, ultimately bringing our communities together and enhancing stability for everyone ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#)).

10. Local Governance and the Need for Stronger Social Audits

Social audits are participatory mechanisms at the local level where citizens actively monitor and evaluate government performance and policy implementation. These audits facilitate closer ties with government, enhanced accountability, delivery of public services, as well as local development. These also help to assess the policy complexities and evolving expectations of the citizen at the grassroots level. Strengthening social audits is a vital key to building transparency and trust at the grassroots level. Traditionally, accountability was in place by the "supply side" of governance through political checks, administrative rules, auditing, and law enforcement. However, these top-down mechanisms have often proved to have limited success in both developed and developing countries. Recently, the "demand side" of governance has been in focus, aiming to empower citizens—especially the poor. It is directed towards seeking greater accountability from public officials and service providers. This approach enhances citizens' engagement with public servants and politicians in an informed and constructive way. ([Rousseau, 1762/2010](#); [Malena, Forster, & Singh, 2004](#)). When communities have a clear voice in tracking public services and spending, the bond between citizens and local authorities deepens. This isn't just good governance—it's how a meaningful, people-centered social contract takes root and grows strong.

11. From Theory to Text: The Constitution as the Social Contract's Culmination

Constitutions are vital social contracts that harmonize the individual interests of diverse groups with the broader needs of society as a whole. An in-depth evaluation of the constitution of Bangladesh is crucial to ensure that it genuinely reflects the social contract of its citizens. It should incorporate the cherished values and morals that define their identity. It is essential that the constitutional initiatives create an environment where the Constitution operates authentically as a social contract.

While examining this issue from the perspective of Bangladesh, it is needed to resolve the controversies and complexities that challenge the constitution's role as a social contract in post-movement Bangladesh. Upholding the rule of law and ensuring due process are critical, and these elements must resonate with the spiritual, moral, and ethical fabric of Bangladeshi society. The concept of "checks and balances" is a fundamental yet intricate aspect of our Constitution. The constitution is designed and meant to create a clear separation of powers among

different branches of government. This principle is immensely important because it works as a protection to prevent any one branch from becoming too powerful. However, the specifics of how this separation works can sometimes be misleading. Understanding and clarifying these elements is essential for maintaining the integrity of our democratic system ([Snyder, 2017](#)).

12. Toward a Just, Inclusive, and Enduring Social Contract

The correlation between a balanced social contract through economic, social, and political liberalization and the unprecedented rise in living standards is not merely coincidental. This transformation has lifted millions out of poverty, both globally and within our region. Again, some of the authoritarian regimes also achieved phenomenal development by eradicating enormous poverty. Ultimately, without Rousseau's notion of the general will, development risks becoming an abstract, technocratic exercise - disconnected from the cultural roots and normative justice that provides it with meaning. But both models have inherent deficiencies in explaining the environmental impact of contemporary development policies, and it is necessary that we find and remedy such issues without delay. In order to gain a sustainable future for all, we must integrate moral values into the fabric of our social contract. This inclusion is a requirement for a fair and equitable society ([Snyder, 2017](#)).

As the idea of the social contract spans across borders, it substantiates that success lies not in replication but in relevance. It thrives where governments listen—where they answer not only to the economic struggles of their people but also to their hopes, fears, and sense of belonging. A just society cannot be structured with numbers alone; it must be shaped by empathy, trust, and shared aspirations. To advance together, we must resist the temptations of narrow nationalism and the harmful politics of division. Real progress takes place when everyone feels seen, heard, and valued—when no one is left behind in the story of the nation ([Snyder, 2017](#)).

13. Conclusion

In this crucial period of political unrest and rising authoritarianism, we need to reinforce the social contract as a tool for justice, participation, and a shared vision. Some governments achieve strong economic growth but impede personal freedoms and erode public trust. Progress without liberty is not true advancement; it simply masks the underlying fractures in the relationship between the state and society (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; [Sen, 1999](#)).

To restore the social contract to its rightful place, societies must find space for reason and emotion, law and legitimacy, and rights and responsibility. Rousseau's concept of the general will must be balanced with Hume's emphasis on custom, history, and feeling. ([Snyder, 2017](#)). A just society is not technocratic or tribal—it is moral, it is inclusive, and it is reflective. It should be developed from within, focusing on the values, voices, and vulnerabilities of the people.

In Bangladesh, this renewal is not theoretical—it is urgent. The depletion of electoral credibility, erosion of civil liberties, and distributive justice have shattered the moral foundation of governance. In spite of ongoing economic growth, the social contract has become increasingly fragile, especially for individuals at the margins ([Human Rights Watch, 2023](#); [Rousseau, 1762/2010](#)). Bangladesh always has the option to move beyond the binaries of authoritarian efficiency and democratic complexities to restore dignity, cohesion, and inclusive governance. It must craft a model rooted in local values but guided by universal ideals. It also needs to combine tradition with change, ensuring development benefits everyone, not just the powerful.

14. Recommendations

The following recommendations are based on the preceding objective discussion and analysis, presented without bias.

14.1 General Recommendations for Strengthening the Social Contract and Advancing Sustainable Development

1. It is highly recommended to institutionalize transparent electoral processes by supporting genuinely independent and well-resourced electoral bodies to ensure free and fair elections (see sections 7.2, 9).
2. Involving citizens through methods like social audits and structured engagement is recommended to improve government accountability and transparency (see section 10).

3. Protecting civil liberties and freedom of expression is advised, as they nourish democratic resilience and accountability (see sections 7.1, 8.3).
4. Implementing equitable development strategies can close socio-economic gaps, foster national unity, and cultivate a collective sense of progress (see section 7.3).
5. Governance frameworks that thoughtfully integrate cultural and ethical values can enhance legitimacy while harmonizing with universal human rights principles (see section 12).
6. Giving priority to balanced urban–rural development supports fairness, eases structural tensions, and helps reduce inequalities across different regions (see section 8.5).
7. Strengthening civil society and international partnerships is essential for effective governance oversight, serving as a powerful catalyst for sustainable, rights-based development and fostering meaningful positive change. (see section 10).
8. It is strongly suggested that development be culture-sensitive to sustain and promote human dignity, community cohesion, and unique aspirations (see section 8.3).
9. Further study and research are encouraged to explore how Rousseau’s ideals of popular consent and Hume’s emphasis on human sentiments can be integrated to design more pragmatic and resilient governance models (see section 6).

14.2 Recommendations Specific to Bangladesh

1. It is crucial to stop the political marginalization of opposition groups through thoughtful legal and institutional reforms that promote pluralism and inclusive participation (see section 9.1).
2. Supporting the independence and operational autonomy of the Election Commission will help restore public confidence and safeguard electoral integrity (see sections 7.2, 7.4, 8.2, 9).
3. Reformation of laws like the Digital Security Act with a specific focus on protecting fundamental freedoms is strictly recommended to reinforce the pillars of democratic governance (see section 9.2).
4. Enhancing equitable access to basic services for marginalized and disadvantaged communities is essential to promote social justice and inclusive development (see sections 7.4, 8.4 9.1).
5. By thoughtfully blending Bangladesh's cultural heritage and values with governance and aligning them with universal human rights, we can establish a distinct and legitimate path forward. (see section 12)
6. Targeted efforts to reduce urban-rural socio-economic disparities will support inclusive growth and social cohesion (see section 8.5).
7. Expanding inclusive social protection networks can ensure better healthcare access and help alleviate poverty for the most vulnerable populations (see section 10).
8. Guaranteeing a full separation of powers, especially judicial independence, would strengthen democratic institutions and enhance public trust (see section 9, 11).
9. It is advised to protect press freedom by ending censorship, harassment, and intimidation in order to maintain an informed and empowered citizenry (see section 9.2).
10. Addressing enforced disappearances and extrajudicial killings through independent investigations and accountability mechanisms is strictly recommended to uphold human rights and the rule of law (see section 9.2).
11. Reorientation of national development strategies towards holistic, inclusive, and equitable wealth distribution is imperative to lay the foundation for sustainable prosperity (see sections 7.3,7.4, 8.4.).

12. Countering state-driven misinformation and fabricated narratives by promoting fact-based public communication and media literacy is recommended (see section 9.3).
13. Strengthening constitutional and local governance accountability mechanisms is essential to mitigating authoritarian tendencies and reinforcing democratic legitimacy (see Section 10).

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